

Deliverable 1.4.3

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Authors	Namrata Kale, Steffen Neumann, Robert Glen, Timothy Ebbels, Jianliang Gao, Nouredin Sadawi, Ibrahim Karaman, Ola Spjuth, Marco Capuccini, Pablo Moreno, Antonio Rosato, Michael van Vliet, Merlijn van Rijswijk, David Johnson, Kenneth Haug, Philippe Rocca-Serra, Sijin He
Abstract: This deliverable is a comprehensive report of the PhenoMeNal consortium's activities and performance towards meeting the objectives and goals of the project from September 2016 (M13) - February 2017 (M18) inclusive.	

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this third reporting period from September 2016 to February 2017, the PhenoMeNaL consortium continued to focus on its three main activities (Networking, Service and Joint Research Activities) to pursue the project's objectives towards development of an e-infrastructure for processing and analysis of metabolomics data including applications for the wider scientific community. Our infrastructure can be easily reused in other domain fields, requiring only the implementation of container images and wrappers for the tools of the desired domain (proteomics, genomics, astronomy, etc), according to our guidelines. Further development of the PhenoMeNaL Virtual Research Environment (VRE), known as the Cloud Research Environment (CRE) portal¹ included the release of the service catalogue, the PhenoMeNaL App library² with 32 applications for data analysis, software pipelines for fast and secure data transfers between the PhenoMeNaL VRE and repositories like MetaboLights³, scale-up of tools and testing including the first PhenoMeNaL release 2017.02 code-named "Alanine", reproducible and standardised workflows, establishment of links with other e-infrastructures and standard communities in form of working groups, establishment of links with publishers to support data standards and depositions and overall compliance of the project with the Ethical, Legal and Social Implications (ELSI). The Centre For Advanced Studies, Research And Development In Sardinia (CRS4)⁴ was added as a beneficiary, following the acceptance of the Grant Amendment submitted in the previous reporting period.

1.1. Description of work performed and main results

As part of networking activities, a second stakeholder working group was initiated. The group involves practitioners in clinical metabolomics and is currently working towards supporting the transition of metabolomics from clinical research towards clinical practice. A joint Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)⁵ and industry panel meeting was organised in November 2016 to review the project activities and seek independent advice on the technical developments, sustainability and ethical constraints within the project. Dissemination and outreach included regular blog posts on the website, presentation, and posters in conferences. Online tutorials and screencasts were made

¹ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/home>

² <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library>

³ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

⁴ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/about/partners-3/>

⁵ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/about/management-structure/>

available via the website and “help” pages on the PhenoMeNal portal. Privacy and ethics was integrated across all work packages (WPs) including implementation of data provider forms, revisiting the consent forms for the PhenoMeNal use cases and revision of the data management plan with respect to the data use within the PhenoMeNal infrastructure. Representatives from each partner were nominated as data governance managers who ensured that any data submitted for use within the consortium followed the ELSI guidelines. A data controller was also nominated to monitor the data acquisition and management.

The PhenoMeNal release is planned for the end of February with the proposition to include the following features on the PhenoMeNal CRE portal:

- VRE portal can be deployed through third party cloud providers, such as OpenStack⁶, Amazon AWS⁷, and others.
- Users are allowed to use PhenoMeNal hosting Galaxy instance and they are allowed to create their own Galaxy⁸ account on PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance⁹.
- More than 30 Apps in App Library are available for users to browse and search.
- Users are able to login with their Google, LinkedIn, and ORCID, and institutional accounts through Elixir Authentication and Authorisation.

⁶ <https://www.openstack.org>

⁷ <https://aws.amazon.com>

⁸ <https://galaxyproject.org>

⁹ <http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu>

2. OBJECTIVES, ACHIEVEMENTS MANAGEMENT

WORK AND

PROGRESS, PROJECT

2.1. Project objectives for the period

During the period, the consortium has continued to work towards the following general project objectives:

- To integrate existing open source tools and methods for the management, dissemination and computational analysis of very large datasets of human metabolic phenotyping and genomic data into a secure and sustainable e-infrastructure.
- To operate and consolidate the PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure based on existing internal and external HPC and grid resources, including the EGI, and to extend it to worldwide grid infrastructures.
- To improve and scale up tools within the infrastructure to cope with very large datasets.
- To establish technology for a water-tight audit trail for the processing of human metabolic phenotyping data from the raw data acquisition all the way to the generation of high-level biomedical insights.
- To establish privacy-protection methods that allow working with highly sensitive molecular phenotype data.
- To foster the worldwide adoption of PhenoMeNal through a wide range of outreach, dissemination, networking and training activities.
- To develop a model to ensure sustainability of PhenoMeNal.

These project objectives were pursued through the following combination of project networking activities (WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4), service activities (WP5 and WP6) and joint research activities (WP7, WP8 and WP9):

- Establishment of extra-consortium links with other e-infrastructures, scientific communities and publishers.

- Revised version of the PhenoMeNal App Library, the service catalogue listing 32 applications most of which are available via Galaxy workflows and/or Jupyter¹⁰ environments through the VRE. The user can browse, search or filter these tools by functionality (e.g., annotation, statistical analysis or pre-/post-processing), approach or technique (e.g., metabolomics, lipidomics, glycomics or isotopic labelling analysis) or instrument data types (e.g., MS or NMR).
- Specified and integrated two pipelines: one for data imported from MetaboLights (including the data transfer mechanisms), and a second pipeline for data to be submitted to MetaboLights.
- First working versions of various analysis pipelines: Sacurine data analysis use-case, Fluxomics use-case and OpenMS Uppsala use-case.
- Creation of cloud-ready VMI's for the Galaxy and Jupyter user-facing web applications. These VMI's are available on the PhenoMeNal public container registry.
- Testing of software packaged in containers to run on scalable cloud infrastructure, including the Google Cloud Platform¹¹ (GCP), Amazon Web Services (AWS) and four different OpenStack installations (EMBL-EBI Embassy cloud, two different installations of the German scientific de.NBI cloud¹² and the commercial Swedish operator CityCloud¹³)
- A local installation of the PhenoMeNal compute environment (Kubernetes + Galaxy) has been installed at Imperial College (ICL). This is used for development and testing of the processing pipeline for sensitive data that must not leave the ICL data center.
- Online tutorials¹⁴ including screencasts to disseminate and promote the service provided by PhenoMeNal across a wide-range of scientific and industrial sectors.
- Additions to the developer and technical documentation available at the PhenoMeNal Wiki¹⁵.
- Converting the National Phenome Center¹⁶ (NPC) pre-processing pipeline for MSdata to use ISA standards.

¹⁰ <http://jupyter.org>

¹¹ <https://cloud.google.com>

¹² <https://www.denbi.de>

¹³ <https://www.citycloud.com>

¹⁴ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/home>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki>

- A process for checking ELSI compliance for the data sets in use across the project is now in operation.
- Developed a proposition to position PhenoMeNal as hub for FAIRifying Metabolomics data in the European Open Science Cloud¹⁷.

The main deliverables achieved during this period were:

No.	Deliverable name	WP No	Lead participant	Delivery date	Status
D9.2.2	<i>PhenoMeNal</i> -Data Virtual Machine image to enable sharing and dissemination of standardised and processed omics data to participating online repositories, like MetaboLights	9	IPB	M14	Submitted
D9.2.3	<i>Services</i> Virtual Machine Image to facilitate the PhenoMeNal toolsets and pipelines, both locally and in the grid.	9	IPB	M16	Submitted
D3.2	Report on establishing and maintaining relations with publishers for supporting data deposition	3	UoB	M16	Submitted
D1.4.3	Bi-annual Progress Report	1	EMBL-EBI	M18	Submitted

¹⁶ <http://www.imperial.ac.uk/phenome-centre>

¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-open-science-cloud>

D1.5.2	Updated Data management plan	1	EMBL-EBI	M18	Submitted
D3.3.1	Web-based Tutorial release 1“Metabolomics Data Deposition and Analysis through PhenoMeNal”, in the form of video clips	3	UoB	M18	Submitted
D4.2	Report describing the activity and outputs of working groups	4	CIRMMP	M18	Submitted
D8.3	nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules	8	UOXF	M18	Submitted
D9.2.4	Compute VMIs to enable standardised compute capabilities for all the grid supplying partners	9	IPB	M18	Submitted

Table 1. List of deliverables submitted until M13 - M18

Milestones achieved during this period:

No	Milestone name	WP No	Lead participant	Delivery date	Status
MS3.1	First web tutorial online	3	UoB	M18	Achieved

Table 2. List of Milestones achieved until M13 - M18

2.2. Work Progress and Achievements during this period

WP2 - Sustainability of PhenoMeNal

WP Leader: University of Leiden (UL)

The main achievement during this period are:

- Interaction with key players involved in the European Open Science Cloud initiative (EOSC), resulting in the establishment of a metabolomics and phenomics node as one of the first nodes of the EOSC. This node will be launched on March 10, 2017¹⁸. PhenoMeNal, together with the EBI-MetaboLights¹⁹ repository are key components of the node. Positioning of PhenoMeNal in the EOSC is key to for the long-term sustainability, as we expect to secure long-term funding from the EOSC for the upkeep of our services.
- Established good links with other e-infrastructure initiatives (like ELIXIR²⁰) and research infrastructures in biomedicine (like BBMRI²¹ and ISBE²²). In particular, we have taken steps to set up a Metabolomics platform in ELIXIR.

¹⁸ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/2017/02/20/fairifying-metabolomics-and-phenomics-data-in-the-eosc/>

¹⁹ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

²⁰ <https://www.elixir-europe.org>

²¹ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/about/partners-3/>

²² <http://project.isbe.eu>

- Worked towards broad acceptance and involvement of users of PhenoMeNal, to create a large user base.
- Phenomenal comprises a rather complex technical architecture. To support this, we have contributed to the development of e-infrastructure frameworks necessary for our project, and for sustainability issues pushed as many as possible upstream to be maintained by the original developers. Examples include contributions so that the Galaxy framework and the Luigi workflow engine can schedule jobs on a Kubernetes cluster, and contributions to containers for both OpenMS and Bioconductor projects.

A summary of the progress in this period:

Task 2.1 Report on other e-infrastructures, users, investments in the field of metabolomics, biomarkers and biobanks for supporting policy developments

The work was concentrated on establishing good links with other e-infrastructure initiatives, and the European Open Science Cloud in particular. We have obtained a Letter of Support of the Director of ELIXIR, Niklas Blomberg (Annex 3.1) and a MoU between the EuroBioImaging²³ Multimodal Molecular Imaging Node coordinated by the University of Torino and the Instruct Core Center - CERM University of Florence and CIRMMP²⁴ mentioning PhenoMeNal (Annex 3.2).

We are in the process of establishing a Metabolomics platform within ELIXIR, similar to the existing Proteomics platform. The purpose of this platform to discuss on a regular basis the common infrastructures and services needed by the European metabolomics community and provide feedback to the ELIXIR management. Topics to discuss in this platform are the main needs of the metabolomics community (at different levels) with regards to life science computing related infrastructure, including among others topics, public databases, data standards, open analysis tools and cloud-based solutions. In the fast-moving field of computational services, it is of utmost importance to keep emerging needs, developments, and investments aligned and prevent dead-end developments. In addition, other more general needs (in the wider context of ELIXIR) could be outlined in the context of e.g. multi-omics data integration.

We are in close contact with the initiators of the GO FAIR initiative²⁵. The GO FAIR initiative is an early-mover-driven 'bottom up' initiative of several member states, aiming to (a) follow the recommendations of the High-Level Expert Group for the EOSC and (b)

²³ <http://www.eurobioimaging.eu>

²⁴ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/about/partners-3/>

²⁵ <http://www.dtls.nl/go-fair-european-open-science-cloud/>

to help kick-start the implementation phase of the EOSC. “GO FAIR” starts working on a trusted environment where public and private sector partners can deposit, find, access, exchange and reuse each other’s data, workflows and other research objects. The initiators of “GO FAIR” have recognized the value and the general applicability of the approaches developed within PhenoMeNal, and support the idea of building upon PhenoMeNal and the EBI MetaboLights repository to establish a biomedical metabolomics and phenomics node as one of the first nodes in the European Open Science Cloud.

FAIRifying Metabolomics and Phenomics data in the European Open science Cloud

This joint workshop of the PhenoMeNal project and the GO FAIR initiative will explore how to establish a node for FAIRifying metabolomics and phenomics data in the European Open Science Cloud.

PhenoMeNal
Large-Scale Computing for Medical Metabolomics

Share

Thursday 09 MAR 2017 Friday 10 MAR 2017

Add to Calendar

Leiden, the Netherlands

Register

Figure 1. Workshop details on the website for Digital Single Market²⁶.

Future plans:

- Launch the biomedical metabolomics and phenomics node in the European Open Science Cloud, at the end of a workshop with Phenome data experts, Linked Data Experts and key persons of the “GO FAIR” initiative on March 9-10 2017.

²⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/fairifying-metabolomics-and-phenomics-data-european-open-science-cloud>

- Participate in a workshop organized by the proteomics community “The future of proteomics in ELIXIR²⁷” in March 1-2 in Tübingen, Germany, to learn from their approach and to jointly with the proteomics community shape more general needs (in the wider context of ELIXIR) for multi-omics data integration.
- Establish a Metabolomics platform within ELIXIR as a sustained way to discuss the main needs of the metabolomics community (at different levels) with regards to life science computing related infrastructure, including among others topics, public databases, data standards, open analysis tools and cloud-based solutions and to interact with other ‘omics platforms in ELIXIR on multi-omics data integration.
- In conjunction with WP 3 and WP 4, systematically reach out to the biomedical community and give demonstrations of PhenoMeNal at European, regional and national infrastructures / large centers that make regular use of metabolomics, to create a large user base.

WP3 - Dissemination and Outreach

WP leader: University of Birmingham (UoB)

The main achievements during this period are:

- A funding proposal accepted for a training course titled “Cloud-based Metabolomics Data Analysis and Collaboration”. The course is scheduled for September 2017.
- Development of strategy on establishing and maintaining relations with publishers for supporting data deposition.
- Development of web-based tutorials for dissemination and to provide information on PhenoMeNal services.
- Dissemination and Outreach via the Digital Single Market.
- PhenoMeNal flyer.
- Establishment of extra-consortium links with similar initiatives like West-Life²⁸ and THOR²⁹.
- Presentation of PhenoMeNal at various national and international events (see list as appended below).

²⁷ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/events/strategic-workshop-future-proteomics-elixir>

²⁸ <http://about.west-life.eu/>

²⁹ <https://project-thor.eu/>

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period.

Task 3.1 We will initially employ the usual channels for the dissemination of PhenoMeNal tools and services, including scientific publications, workshops and presentations at the metabolomics conferences to reach the wider metabolomics community.

The consortium continued to use the social media channels like Twitter³⁰, Google Plus, slideshare presentations^{31,32} and Facebook to build community around metabolomics and other e-infrastructure initiative to disseminate project outputs and events. YouTube videos^{33,34} have also been produced as part of the project outreach and dissemination.

Figure 2 Google+ post by Ola Spjuth

³⁰ <https://twitter.com/PhnmlH2020>

³¹ <http://www.slideshare.net/ospjuth/analyzing-big-data-in-medicine-with-virtual-research-environments-and-microservices>

³² <http://www.slideshare.net/ospjuth/interoperability-and-scalability-with-microservices-in-science>

³³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6aqcO7PeSdE&feature=youtu.be>

³⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qUuRvC7ySkg&feature=youtu.be&list=PL4Xuww4Q6DbXcRRLCnQrN7s5F_5W4WUJ

SciLifeLab

Interoperability and scalability with microservices

Ola Spjuth <ola.spjuth@farmbio.uu.se>
Science for Life Laboratory
Uppsala University

 PhenoMeNal

UPPSALA
UNIVERSITET

◀ 1 of 21 ▶ SlideShare

Figure 3. Presentation on Slideshare by PhenoMeNal partner Ola Spjuth

We provide large-scale computing for medical metabolomics.

PhenoMeNa is a free e-infrastructure for the European Research Community and beyond, funded by the European Commission.

We provide access to a variety of metabolomics services, and address the needs of users with different levels of expertise.

Our services can be accessed through a single point of entry: the PhenoMeNa portal.

Contact Us
For help with PhenoMeNa, or to send us your feedback, please email us:
✉ phenomenal-help@ebi.ac.uk

Stay in touch
To keep up with PhenoMeNa news, follow us on:
@PhnmlH2020

PhenoMeNa
Large-Scale Computing for Medical Metabolomics

PhenoMeNa (Phenome and Metabolome aNalysis) is a comprehensive, and standardised e-infrastructure to the data processing and analysis pipelines for molecular phenotype data generated by metabolomics applications.

PhenoMeNa will provide services enabling computation and analysis to improve the understanding of the causes and mechanisms underlying health, ageing and diseases.

PhenoMeNa is funded by European Commission's Horizon2020 programme, grant agreement number 654241

phenomenal-h2020.eu

Useful
PhenoMeNa reduces duplication of effort and maximises efficiency for experimental and clinical laboratories of all sizes.

Innovative
PhenoMeNa partners use only validated open-source software, We build state-of-the art European cloud technologies to better serve Metabolomics researchers.

Connected
PhenoMeNa members are major players in metabolomics in Europe with strong links to the global scientific community.

Open
PhenoMeNa is inclusive, we welcome contributions and feedback from all users. We are in sync with current major initiatives for FAIR and open data, and with the European Open Science Cloud.

Partners
The PhenoMeNa consortium comprises 14 participants in the UK and the rest of in Europe who have extensive experience in Metabolomics research, tool development, national metabolomics programme management and service provision in the context of infrastructures and e-infrastructures.

Our objective
To establish a comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure for processing, analysing and information-mining of extremely large medical metabolic phenotype data.

phenomenal-h2020.eu

Figure 4 PhenoMeNa Flyer

Dissemination in conferences and workshops

The partners presented the project on several occasions as part of the dissemination activities. The project website displays all the presentations and posters delivered by the consortium on the “Dissemination & Outreach” page³⁵.

No	Date and location	Event/URL	Type of audience	Contribution	Attendee
1	Sept. 2016, Cambridge, UK	Industry program quarterly meeting	industry, researchers	presentation	EMBL-EBI
2	Sept. 2016, Kraków, Poland	Digital Infrastructures for Research, 2016	researchers, industry, other e- infrastructures	panelist in workshop on VREs for the Open Science Cloud	EMBL-EBI
3	Sept. 2016, Halle, Germany	ODLS 2016 – Ontologies and Data in Life Sciences	data Scientists, researchers	presentation	IPB
4	Sept. 2016, Barcelona, Spain	International Conference on Systems Biology (ICSB 2016)	industry, researchers	presentation	UB
5	Sept. 2016, Montpellier, France	Metabolism & Cancer Symposium, 2nd edition, French Canceropole	clinician, cancer researchers	presentation	INRA

³⁵ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/outreach/>

6	Oct. 2016, Karlsruhe, Germany	Max Rubner Conference 2016: Food Metabolomics	biologists, chemists	presentation	IPB
7	Oct. 2016, Freiburg, Germany	Swiss German Galaxy Tour/Day 2016	bioinformatician, developers	presentation	IPB
8	Oct. 2016, Berlin, Germany	1st Conference of the European Association of Systems Medicine	researchers	presentation	UB
9	Oct. 2016, Rheinfelden, Germany	OpenTox Euro, 2016	toxicologists, researchers	presentation	UU
10	Oct. 2016, Graz, Austria	First CORBEL annual general meeting	BMS ESFRIs	presentation	CIRMMP
11	Oct. 2016, Gothenburg, Sweden	25th anniversary of the Swedish NMR Facility	researchers	presentation	UoB

12	Nov. 2016, Uppsala, Sweden	Big Data in Medicine	data scientists, researchers	presentation	UU
13	Nov. 2016, Cambridge, UK	Genome Campus Software Craftsmanship Community	software developers, bioinformaticians	presentation	EMBL-EBI
14	Nov. 2016, Rome, Italy	A combined CHARME, EMBnet and NETTAB 2016 Workshop	data Scientists, researchers	presentation	EMBL-EBI
15	Nov. 2016, Berlin, Germany	de.NBI SAB Meeting	bioinformaticians	presentation	EMBL-EBI
16	Nov. 2016, London, UK	RCUK Cloud Workshop 2016	Cloud computing experts and companies, data scientists, researchers	presentation	ICL
17	Nov. 2016, Uppsala, Sweden	Informatics & Media department research seminars	researchers	presentation	UOXF
18	Sept. 2016, Barcelona, Spain	International Conference on Systems Biology (ICSB) 2016	industry, researchers	poster	UB

19	Sept. 2016, Heidelberg, Germany	Big Data in Biology and Health	Data scientists, researchers	poster	CRS4
20	Oct. 2016, Jena, Germany	International Study Group for Systems Biology (ISGSB) meeting	biologists, computational modellers, interdisciplinary researchers in the systems biology	poster	UB
21	Oct. 2016, Lund Sweden	Swedish e-Science Academy 2016	data scientists, researchers	poster	UU
22	Dec. 2016, Toulouse, France	French Regional Bioinformatics Conference	bioinformaticians	poster	INRA
23	Jan. 2017, Leiden, The Netherlands	Dutch National Metabolomics Conference (NMC)	Industry, researchers	presentation	UL

Table 3. List of events with PhenoMeNal participation

The project was also disseminated through meetings with other relevant projects and e-infrastructures, publications and newsletters.

- PhenoMeNal: Virtual e-Infrastructure supporting Clinical Research and Metabolism Studies. *Philippe Rocca-Sera*, OeRC News, Nov. 2016.

- “MIDcor, an R-program for deciphering mass interferences in mass spectra of metabolites enriched in stable isotopes³⁶”, Vitaly Selivanov et al, BMC Bioinformatics (2017) 18:88
- Karaman, I., et al. Workflow for Integrated Processing of Multicohort Untargeted 1H NMR Metabolomics Data in Large-Scale Metabolic Epidemiology. *J. Proteome Res.* 2016;15(12):4188-4194. 10.1021/acs.jproteome.6b00125
- Haug, K., Salek, R.M., and Steinbec, C. Global open data management in metabolomics. *Curr Opin Chem Biol.* 2017 Jan 13; 36:58-63. doi: 10.1016/j.cbpa.2016.12.024

A workshop proposal focused on workflows in PhenoMeNal has recently been accepted for hosting in the upcoming Metabolomics 2017³⁷ conference in Australia.

Task 3.2. Using new and already established links we will build a network of e-infrastructure users and resource providers

Some PhenoMeNal consortium members in collaboration with extra-PhenoMeNal institutes have presented a funding proposal to the Region of Sardinia (Italy) for a short training school titled *Cloud-based Metabolomics Data Analysis and Collaboration*. The School is aimed at researchers, graduate-level students and industry professionals. The proposal has now been approved, the resulting course will include a significant PhenoMeNal component, and thus represents a prime dissemination and training opportunity for this project.

Task 3.3 PhenoMeNal will also build a dialog between mass spectrometry and NMR instrument vendors, search engine providers, experimentalists, data resources, and publishers.

The relation with Publishers: Scientific Data Journal, GigaScience and more.

The tools in PhenoMeNal are being developed to support ISA formats³⁸ for importing data into the PhenoMeNal infrastructure, but also for documenting analytical processes, thus tracking transformation output as they are delivered by the workflows. Supporting standardised formats across tools and platforms but also ensuring adoption by key players is central. Nature Publishing Scientific Data³⁹ adoption of ISA allows “data set publications” to be made. The fact that the same format is used by the Metabolights Repository and a publication such as Scientific Data reduces the barrier for adoption for

³⁶ <https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-017-1513-3>

³⁷ <http://metabolomics2017.org>

³⁸ <http://isa-tools.org/>

³⁹ <http://www.nature.com/sdata/publish/submission-guidelines>

end users Data Descriptors and simplifies procedures. In a similar initiative, as part of a collaboration with the PhenoMeNal partner UOXF, the content of the GigaDB database⁴⁰ is being exported in ISA-format. Owing to the nature of data production, the bulk of the data found in those publications belongs to the genomic and transcriptomic domains but it showcases how the metadata format can flexibly accommodate different datatypes. For the PhenoMeNal infrastructure, it means data from different omics can be brought in seamlessly. It can therefore make full use and derive benefit from both Springer Nature's Scientific Data and OUP/BGI GigaScience journals through their support of the ISA format. PhenoMeNal's use and export of metadata in ISA formats, as well as raw and derived data in standard formats (i.e. mzML and nmrML), being developed as outputs of PhenoMeNal WP8, provide the required interoperability elements to link to the journals (see D3.2 Report on establishing and maintaining relations with publishers for supporting data deposition). More recently, fruitful conversations with Elsevier have taken place and meetings have been planned to outline ISA adoption for their data support needs. In parallel, the consortium plans to establish agreements with publishers to support metabolomics data deposition. For the publisher stakeholders, to have the possibility to mobilize metadata store in ISA document is a driver of adoption. To this end, use of the ISA-explorer tool to browse, search and visualise the data available is an enabler, as demonstrated with NPG Scientific Data and with GigaDB. Furthermore, through involvement with NIH BD2K Biocaddie⁴¹ and Elixir-UK, ISA-explorer provides a markup with schema.org elements, thus making datasets discovery by search engines easier and more efficient, thus potentially allowing for an increase in impact of experimental work published with the metadata framework adopted by PhenoMeNal.

Task 3.5 We will develop and disseminate a web tutorial about the standards and the software workflows established by the PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure.

A screencast⁴² on the use of Galaxy workflow has been produced which is available on the project website (see D3.3.1 Web-based Tutorial release 1 about "Metabolomics Data Deposition and Analysis through PhenoMeNal", in form of video clips).

Future Plans:

- Video tutorials of the NPC/NMR processing workflow will be prepared by ICL.
- Write publications on the wider applicability of the approaches developed in PhenoMeNal to other scientific communities.

⁴⁰ <http://gigadb.org/site/about>

⁴¹ <https://biocaddie.org>

⁴² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6aqcO7PeSdE&feature=youtu.be>

- Approaching publishers for data deposition.
- Organisation of training workshops for the user community.

WP4 – Interfacing with Biomedical European Infrastructures

WP leader: Consorzio Interuniversitario Risonanze Magnetiche di Metallo Proteine (CIRMMP)

The main achievements during this period are:

- D4.1 was completed. This deliverable provided input to the PhenoMeNal development regarding some requirements of other European, regional and national infrastructures / large centers that make regular use of metabolomics, based on the replies of 20 different stakeholders to a survey. This includes 4 private companies.
- A second working group involving clinicians was established, with a specific focus on the computational services required to support the use of metabolomics in clinical practice
- PhenoMeNal was presented at the annual meeting of the CORBEL project (<http://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html>)

A summary of of the progress of the work in this reporting period:

Task 4.1. Collecting and reporting on the requirements of research and/or industry centers that produce or make use of metabolomics.

We analysed the results of the survey that was distributed, both as an online survey on surveymonkey and via email to selected contacts (see D1.4.2). The questionnaire addressed the following topics:

- Type of e-infrastructure
- Computational requirements
- Storage requirements
- Data throughput
- Software requirements

The analysis of the questionnaire received has been reported in deliverable D4.1, which was submitted at the end of August 2016. Among its most relevant conclusions, the analysis indicated that European centres are currently not making systematic use of

either cloud computing or cloud storage, thereby creating an opportunity that Phenomenal is strategically positioned to address. Quantitative indications on the computing resources consumed and the storage resources available locally at the various centers provided possible references for the scale of operation of the Phenomenal infrastructure. Finally, some specific software requirements were highlighted, which were already included in the Phenomenal development plans. In particular, these concerned the use of Galaxy as a workflow manager and of R for statistical analysis.

Problems and challenges encountered

The initial flow of replies to the survey was lower than anticipated, which required several rounds of e-mail reminders. We believe that the conclusions reported in the survey are nevertheless relevant, also because of the good homogeneity of the large majority of the information.

Task 4.2: Establish and convene working groups involving the Phenomenal consortium as well as participants in other biomedical infrastructure and research projects

Following upon the plans outlined in D1.4.2, a visit by one Phenomenal representative to the node of the ISBE Research Infrastructure at Wageningen University took place in September 2016. As a consequence, a working group was implemented with the main aim to work on an overview of the use and applications of metabolomics in systems biology. An initial draft of this document is being finalized under the coordination of Dr. Edoardo Saccenti, one of the members of the Wageningen node, and will be circulated to all Phenomenal partners. The document might be submitted in the form a review to a peer-reviewed scientific journal in the field.

A second stakeholder working group⁴³ was established, involving clinicians. The group was established as part of the outcome of the clinical workshop in Barcelona in May 2016⁴⁴. The goals of this group are as follows:

- Represent clinical metabolomics practitioners as target users of Phenomenal. Initially these will primarily be clinical research scientists, with the expectation that those involved in translating metabolomics technologies to routine clinical practice will join.
- Advise what functions are required in Phenomenal tools and workflows by clinical users. This may involve defining specific use cases/scenarios.

⁴³ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/outreach/work-groups/>

⁴⁴ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/outreach/workshops-training/2/>

- If tools that address the functionalities of point 2 are implemented in PhenoMeNal, participate in user testing.
- Work towards a manuscript or report which describes a vision for metabolomics in clinical research/practice, focussing on the role of computational workflows such as those provided by Phenomenal.

The coordinator of the working group is Dr. Hutan Ashrafiyan, a bariatric surgeon based at Imperial College London. So far, the working group has been meeting online on approximately a bi-monthly basis.

A part of the activities of work package WP4 is to make ESFRI infrastructures aware of the activities and services of PhenoMeNal. To achieve this goal, it seemed most efficient to tackle primarily the partnership of the CORBEL⁴⁵ (Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services) project, which is a consortium involving nearly all biomedical ESFRIs. In particular, a presentation of the PhenoMeNal achievements was delivered at the first annual general meeting of CORBEL in October 2016 in Graz.

Future Plans

- Finalize the document by the working group on metabolomics in systems biology by spring 2017, and submit it for publication (led by CIRMMMP).
- We are in discussion with GA4GH⁴⁶ (Global Alliance for Genomics in Healthcare) to increase global visibility and collaboration with PhenoMeNal (led by ICL and EBI).
- Define a (broad) topic for the position paper by the clinical working group.
- Participate in a Roundtable to discuss on the exploitation of Research Infrastructures, both physical and electronic, by European researchers in biological and biomedical sciences, during the biennial meeting INSTRUCT⁴⁷, the European Integrated Infrastructure for Structural Biology, in Brno on May 24-26, 2017⁴⁸.
- Evaluate interactions with other e-Science initiatives (VREs, EGI competence centers ...)

⁴⁵ <http://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html>

⁴⁶ <http://genomicsandhealth.org>

⁴⁷ <https://www.structuralbiology.eu>

⁴⁸ <https://www.structuralbiology.eu/update/biennial2017>

WP5 – Operations and maintenance of PhenoMeNal GRID/CLOUD

WP Leader: Uppsala University

During this period, much of the work was focused on developments for the upcoming PhenoMeNal VRE release (codename: Alanine). The main achievements during this period are as follows:

T5.1: Operation and Maintenance of the GRID/cloud infrastructure

Deployment

One of the previously chosen deployment and orchestration frameworks (MANTL) was discontinued by the upstream developers (funded by Cisco), so we decided to focus on the other tested candidate framework, Kubernetes. Existing kubernetes deployment frameworks are not yet fully supporting the functionality to instantiate and tear down kubernetes clusters on a regular basis, but more on the establishment of long-running installations which is more common in industry. This necessitated us to develop a novel deployment framework, KubeNow⁴⁹ where you can rapidly deploy, scale, and tear down your Kubernetes clusters on public and private cloud systems (e.g., AWS, GCE and OpenStack) as well as local clusters (Vagrant/Virtualbox). KubeNow is a thin layer on top of existing established software⁵⁰ (Terraform, Packer, Ansible and kubeadm), see Figure 3 below. Following this approach, we provide a simple, light-weight, tool for Kubernetes provisioning, and a critical tool needed for PhenoMeNal. By deploying a KubeNow cluster the user will get:

- A Kubernetes cluster up and running in less than 10 minutes (provisioned with kubeadm⁵¹);
- Weave⁵² networking;
- Traefik⁵³ HTTP reverse proxy and load balancer;
- Cloudflare⁵⁴ dynamic DNS integration;
- GlusterFS⁵⁵ distributed file system.

⁴⁹ <https://github.com/kubenow/KubeNow>

⁵⁰ For definitions see: <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki/Vocabulary-and-definitions-in-PhenoMeNal>

⁵¹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/getting-started-guides/kubeadm/>

⁵² <https://www.weave.works/>

⁵³ <https://traefik.io/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.cloudflare.com/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.gluster.org/>

Figure 5: KubeNow delivers kubernetes clusters with dynamic DNS integration, networks, load balancing, and a distributed file system. KubeNow wraps around existing industry-standard tools and is used to deploy PhenoMeNal VREs.

The workflow environment Galaxy has also been integrated into the main deployment process of the PhenoMeNal CRE, which means that users deploying a private PhenoMeNal immediately get a working instance of Galaxy that is secured for their own private usage only.

Infrastructure testing

KubeNow follows the Infrastructure as Code (IaC) paradigm, which is the process of deploying and provisioning the computing resources through machine readable definition files. This paradigm has the benefit of automating the deployment, and also allows one to define the infrastructure as a set of files that have enough information to replicate the infrastructure over time and at different data centers. This programmatic approach to infrastructure definition makes possible to apply the same best practices that are used for software testing to infrastructure testing, including version control. In practice, every time we make a commit to the repository that holds the KubeNow infrastructure definition, the continuous integration (CI) process is triggered and the infrastructure is automatically lifted and tested on the supported cloud providers.

VRE installations

PhenoMeNal VREs can be instantiated on public and private cloud IaaS providers as well as local servers on an on-demand basis. Two notable installations are the reference installation reported below in T5.2, and the on-premises installations reported below in T5.4. Apart from this, the *de.NBI installations*⁵⁶ deserve mentioning.

The German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI) is a network of partners that provide bioinformatics services in different areas. Recently, Germany joined the

⁵⁶ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/2017/01/13/phenomenal-meets-denbi/>

European life-sciences infrastructure for biological information (ELIXIR) as a full member, and de.NBI is establishing the German node in ELIXIR. Several of the service centers are currently establishing a multi-site de.NBI cloud as the basis for a future-oriented compute structure in Germany. The Bielefeld-Gießen Resource Center for Microbial Bioinformatics (BiGi) has two independent OpenStack installations (on different hardware platforms and independent software versions) operated by the CeBiTec at Bielefeld University and the Bioinformatics team at Giessen University. We have been able to lift PhenoMeNal VREs at both sites.

Phenomenal infrastructure, a well planned (and well punned) idea by S. Neumann from Halle at the SAB meeting @denbiOffice @ELIXIREurope

Figure 6. PhenoMeNal and de.NBI on Twitter

T5.2: Operation and Maintenance of the PhenoMeNal VRC

Reference installation at EMBL-EBI Embassy Cloud

This installation has been described in detail in earlier deliverables. The following two advancements have been recently added:

- PhenoMeNal docker registry now runs on top of Kubernetes on the Embassy Cloud and uses an s3 object store as data backend provided by EBI. These two measures greatly improve the availability of the service.

- Two permanent Kubernetes deployments with shared file systems, one that hosts the PhenoMeNal public instance and a second devoted to tool and workflow testing. Both instances include open Galaxy deployments which can be used freely by external users.

EBI Portal mediated automatic VRE deployment

In close collaboration with the TSI Team at the EBI, PhenoMeNal developers wrote AngularJS software for the PhenoMeNal Gateway Portal to trigger the deployment of PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Environments (VRE) using API facilities provided by the EBI Portal automatic deployment system. KubeNow was interfaced with this software layer, providing a single click setup for the PhenoMeNal cloud VRE⁵⁷. The scripts are designed to work with the EBI Portal and consumed from the Phenomenal Gateway/Portal (developed in WP6). The process to make this mechanism feature-complete is ongoing.

T5.3: Provisioning of the PhenoMeNal Services

Two of the main technological components for PhenoMeNal have been successfully bridged: the use of software containers in a scalable infrastructure and their user-friendly access through workflow environments. PhenoMeNal developers contributed to the open source Galaxy project the ability for it to run inside a container orchestrator system (Kubernetes) and to offload computational jobs to containers running within the same container orchestrator system. Additionally, the Galaxy-Kubernetes deployment was written using the Helm Kubernetes package manager, allowing external users to lift our Galaxy setup in any Kubernetes installation, regardless of how it is deployed. Galaxy is the most popular workflow environment in the context of Bioinformatics.

To reduce the risk of being locked to a single workflow environment, PhenoMeNal developers replicated the same abilities of running within a container orchestrator and offloading jobs for the Luigi workflow environment. Luigi is a workflow environment developed by Spotify, and has gained a lot of momentum within the data science community in the past few years. Together, these developments guarantee the ability of PhenoMeNal users to access scalable infrastructure based on containers through workflow environments.

Testing in the field of containers is not well defined within the software engineering community, and in order to fill this void we have contributed to define and implement new testing strategies. Through our Container Testing workshop (Nov 14-15, 2016 at EBI/Hinxton) we have established best practices of automatically testing tools that have been containerised within our continuous integration system. During the same meeting, partners also presented a method to test entire workflows automatically within Galaxy.

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/phnmnl/cloud-deploy-kubenow>

We are now in a position to not only test tools individually within their containers, but run integration tests of our tools as they are involved in different workflows. Both tool testing and workflow testing are executed in the same container orchestration context that any PhenoMeNal VRE deployment uses.

T5.4: Operation and Maintenance of a reference site for analysis on private data

In collaboration with UU, ICL has implemented a local instance of Phenomenal to test the feasibility of processing sensitive data in a local compute environment. The implementation is being scaled up to establish performance and reliability criteria in a different computational architecture. The implementation at ICL uses KubeNow via Vagrant and virtualbox to run on an 80-core local server with Linux CentOS 7.5. For the tests we have access to several internal datasets⁵⁸, including MESA (Multi-Ethnic Study of Atherosclerosis), to evaluate workflows such as the NPC pre-processing pipeline and BATMAN⁵⁹.

T5.5: Operation and Maintenance of Continuous Integration system

The PhenoMeNal Continuous Integration system Jenkins, previously reported in D5.1, is operational.

Future Plans

- Further developments of local server VRE installations to improve stability and performance
- Make the integration between PhenoMeNal-KubeNow and EBI Portal feature-complete
- Develop means for federation of data and compute resources
- Extend the testing coverage for containers, workflow and infrastructure
- Explore integration with EGI federated cloud
- Develop the high-availability features of KubeNow when the dependency kubeadm supports it, or move to a deployment scheme that provides high-availability features
- Implement shared block-storage cloud integrations for Amazon and Google clouds, to improve performance
- Move Luigi and Jupyter deployments in Kubernetes to the Helm package manager

⁵⁸ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/documentation/2/>

⁵⁹ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/batman>

WP6 – PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway

WP leader: European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL-EBI)

The main achievements during this period are:

- Implemented the automatic update of the metadata of application containers in App Library through their corresponding README files in GitHub.
- Implemented Filter for focused browsing of application containers.
- Information in “Help” section is automatically updated with PhenoMeNal Wiki on GitHub
- Set up mechanism to collect statistics on VRE Gateway usage.
- Elixir Authorisation and Authentication for enabling the single sign-on service has been integrated with CRE Gateway for offering user login and registration services.
- EBI web services for cloud research environment deployment in CRE gateway has been developed by TSI at EMBL-EBI in collaboration with ELIXIR.
- Designed Landing page including registration and terms of use to include ELSI processes.

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period

Task 6.2 Development of the PhenoMeNal VRC portal

The automatic update of the metadata of application containers in App Library through their corresponding README files in GitHub were developed. At the moment, there are 32 applications listing in the App Library. The Search and Filtering functionalities help users narrow down their application searches based on functionality, approaches and instrument data types as shown in Figure 7 below.

App Library showcases our service catalogue listing 32 applications that are available via Galaxy workflows and Jupyter libraries through the Cloud Research Environment.

Search for Apps Grid List

Functionality

- Preprocessing
- Annotation
- Post-processing
- Statistical Analysis
- Workflows
- Other Tools

Approaches

- Metabolomics
- Isotopic Labelling Analysis
- Lipidomics
- Glycomics

Instrument Data Types

- MS
- NMR
- IR
- Raman
- UV/VIS
- DAD

BATMAN
Bayesian Automated Metabolite Analyser for NMR spectra (BATMAN).

W4M Biosigner
Discovery of significant signatures from omics data.

IPO
A Tool for automated Optimization of XCMS Parameters

W4M LCMS matching
Annotation of MS peaks using matching on a spectra database.

MetFrag-CLI
Command Line Interface for MetFrag.

W4M Metabolights Downloader
Metabolights downloader

W4M Multivariate
PCA, PLS(-DA) and OPLS(-DA) for multivariate analysis of omics data

rNMR
Open source software for identifying and quantifying metabolites in NMR spectra.

W4M Univariate
Univariate statistics.

XCMS
XCMS is a framework for processing and visualization of chromatographically separated and single-spectra mass spectral data.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the PhenoMeNal App library.

A “Help” page was added to the portal menu bar. Information in “Help” section are automatically updated with PhenoMeNal Wiki on GitHub. This section consists of tutorials on the PhenoMeNal project as well as the set up for PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment (CRE). The statistics for the “Gateway” was also set up. This gives a general overview of number of visitors visiting the Gateway, and which countries they are coming from. This page also shows the status of container build to developers.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the statistics page.

As part of deployment of the VRE, Elixir Authorisation and Authentication for enabling the single sign-on service (SSO) was integrated with VRE Gateway for offering user login and registration services. Users can now easily sign in with their existing institutional accounts, or Google, LinkedIn, or ORCID.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the ELIXIR SSO

Figure 10. Screenshot of the login page. The user can login using ORCID, LinkedIn, Google or their institutional account

EBI web services for the PhenoMeNal VRE deployment has been developed by TSI at EMBL-EBI in collaboration with ELIXIR. The Users can now deploy their cloud research environment through the PhenoMeNal gateway using cloud provider of their choice.

Figure 11. Set up of VRE using cloud provider of choice.

Future Plans

- Support cloud research environment deployment on multiple cloud platforms, such as OpenStack, Amazon AWS, Google cloud.
- Constant improvement on the portal based on user feedback.
- Containerise the VRE gateway.

WP7 - Privacy and Ethics

WP leader: Imperial College London (ICL)

The main achievements during this period are:

- Creating a registration process for PhenoMeNal users, both data providers and data analysts.
- Creating a PhenoMeNal data provider form and implementing workflows for ELSI consideration in PhenoMeNal.
- Appointment of Data governance managers in each partner and provision of guidance on their role.
- Creation of a repository of ethical approval documentation for data used in the development of Phenomenal.
- Several preparation meetings for a further ELSI themed workshop in 2017 have taken place to discuss (1) how ELSI requirements as currently in operation in Phenomenal can evolve from a development project environment to an production environment and (2) How Phenomenal can influence the wider community in ELSI. The third ELSI workshop is being planned for Q2-Q4 2017.

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period

Task 7.1 Organise workshops involving Scientific and Technological Advisory board (STAB) and the Management Committee (MC) and other necessary players to devise best practices in handling sensitive human data, taking into account National and Institutional legal policies.

Preparations are underway for the next ELSI workshop which is scheduled for summer 2017.

Task 7.2 Establish and generate a robust workflow for data dissemination and disclosure taking into account guidance for task 7.1.

ELSI requirements continue to evolve as the project develops and PhenoMeNal moves from predominately software/infrastructure design to implementation/data analysis at different institutions. For example, the development version of installation of the

PhenoMeNal research environment has been installed on the MedBio cluster at ICL for analysis of the MESA exemplar data (PhenoMeNal use case data set). This has required discussion and guidance from our ELSI collaborators and the implementation of a process for data use in Phenomenal. Two requirements have been looked at in detail: (1) Is the permission/legal framework in place to use proposed data sets in the testing phase of PhenoMeNal and (2) establishment of a standard process to monitor data use in PhenoMeNal. The ethical/legal approval for each of the datasets in use in PhenoMeNal has been scrutinized to determine that the data use is in concordance with the guidelines.

A registration form was integrated as part of the user login to the PhenoMeNal portal. This was to ensure that PhenoMeNal users are aware of terms and use of PhenoMeNal while using PhenoMeNal for their data analysis.

Figure 12. Screenshot of the login page where the user is prompted to comply with PhenoMeNal terms and conditions.

Task 7.3 Identify governance managers in each collaborating research group who are responsible for overseeing day to day Information Governance issues; developing and maintaining policies, standards, procedures and guidance; coordinating Information Governance in the consortium; and ensuring ongoing compliance from all the project participants.

Each partner has nominated a “data governance manager” responsible for obtaining the relevant information on data used locally or distributed to other partners and to ensure, in collaboration with the Data Controller, that it is ELSI compliant. See Annex 3.3 for role of the “data governance manager.”

Task 7.7 Identify human clinical datasets to test drive development and ensure that the ethical approvals cover use within the PhenoMeNal project, including the non-EC

partner Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB). Provide EC/REA with copies of ethical approvals and related informed consent forms and information materials for patients.

The consent for the continued use of MESA dataset as PhenoMeNal use case (see D7.5 Report to the EC/REA with ethical approvals) within the consortium was obtained. The details have been incorporated in the updated data management plan (D1.5.2).

Future Plans

- We will continue to work with the other Phenomenal partners to monitor application of the ELSI workflows and guidelines throughout the project.

WP8 – Data provenance, compliance and Integrity

WP leader: The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford (UOXF)

The main achievements during this period are:

- Work on modularization of ISA schema data has been carried out.
- Significant improvements in the stability of the software (ISA-API) have been achieved (T8.2), with several rounds of release and testing being done
- National phenome centre adoption of ISA-Tab format (T8.2).
- Implementation of mzml2isa and nmrml2isa software tooling (T8.3)
- nmrML2txt (converts an NMR file to a text file that can be read BATMAN or other tools requiring text files). Is part of the nmrIO package which is being incorporated into PhenoMeNal (T8.3)
- Containerisation and integration with Galaxy for standards tooling (T8.2, T8.3) focusing on input/output operations
- Review and improvements to the specifications for ISA extensions necessary to support the Fluxomics and stable isotope resolved metabolomics studies (towards T8.4)
- Expansion in coverage to terminology support for reporting statistical results (2 new releases of STATO controlled vocabulary, towards T8.4) to cover outlier detection and meta analysis.
- Creation of dedicated terminology for representation quality control elements in submissions and deposition (towards T8.4) and corresponding ISA coding patterns (implementation guidelines) as well as support for aliquot tracking.

All of this activity has been informed by the results of contributions from the metabolomics community via the WP8 survey⁶⁰ completed in the previous reporting period.

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period

T8.3: Data standards exchange formats

Implementation of mzml2isa and nmrml2isa software tooling, towards integration of mzML and nmrML standards for use within PhenoMeNal. These tools automatically extract metadata into ISA-Tab formatted outputs. Containerisation and work to make fit-for-use in Galaxy has been done.

Work detailed in M18 deliverable D8.3 “nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules”.

T8.2: Standards for exchanging experimental and clinical metadata

Further work on modularization of ISA data has been carried out. The ISA API now supports import/export of SRA XML documents (genomics and transcriptomics) and allows NIH Metabolomics Workbench data conversion to ISA formats as well as provides support with export from a popular supplier of targeted metabolomics profiling kits, Biocrates data. This means 650 + studies from the US repository can now be easily mobilized, even if not mirrored in Metabolights.

Efforts have also focused on readying IO operations for a scale up capable of support very large cohorts, in line with potential projected needs for analytical sample processing and molecular phenotyping by means of metabolomics. Following a series of tests which revealed bottlenecks, the ISA API performance has been significantly enhanced. Time required for parsing ISA input grows linearly with the number of samples. It means to it can support import and export of large experimental graphs consisting of tens of thousands of samples and data files metadata. The ISA-API create mode (a feature under development) has been used to test handling large synthetic studies.

Various ISA API features have been containerised as microservices for use in Galaxy. ISA API work has resulted in the completion of 3 pre-released milestones (v0.3-v0.5)⁶¹

Work with national phenome centres to incorporate data standards such as ISA-Tab into their processing pipelines is underway with Imperial College NPC integrating ISA into

⁶⁰ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/documentation/3/>

⁶¹ <https://github.com/ISA-tools/isa-api/milestones?state=closed>

QC pipelines and using the ISA API software. ICL is currently working with Oxford to implement ISA compatible workflows and interfaces to data structures in metabolomics.

The full raw data set from the Sacurine use case (CEA partner) was deposited in the MetaboLights reference repository (as MTBLS404)⁶². The data set (LC-MS analysis of urines from a human cohort) contains 234 raw mzML files: 184 samples, 26 Quality Controls (QC) and 24 reagent blanks. The data were used by the UOXF partner to enrich the ISA-Tab format by including new standard fields for sample metadata (e.g., type of sample and control, order of injection into the instrument, and batch number). MTBLS404 is complementary to the previously deposited MTBLS20⁶³ data set, which focuses on the annotation of urine samples from the Sacurine cohort. Importantly, MTBLS404 is the source of data for the Sacurine workflow (described below).

The availability of validation function via the ISA-API allowed additional testing and batch processing of public MetaboLights datasets. In the light of the work on quality control coding patterns, these batch tests consisting in gulping repository content highlighted a number of irregular shape in the metadata file. This has lead to an additional effort of correction to improve metadata coding quality and deliver optimal updated archive documents. The focus has been on human data available from MetaboLights.

Maintaining precise and computable data provenance information is an important aspect of this project. An analysis of the current situation in the field, especially with respect to biomedical research, resulted in proposal of FAIR-Health principles by BBMRI-ERIC, which are piloted within the provenance information management in PhenoMeNal.

Moreover, through our ongoing investigation into how to model and manage data provenance information associated to the results of metabolomics analysis, we have started (November 2016) a collaboration with the workgroup WG5 "data processing including annotation, analysis, validation, comparability and integration" of ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology. The work is aimed at determining how that standard needs to be extended to properly track metabolomic data provenance information.

⁶² <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/MTBLS404>

⁶³ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/MTBLS20>

T8.5: Maintain documentation and disseminate information

Progress towards documenting and disseminating the work carried out in this work package is going, with extensive documentation being published regarding the standards specifications and standards tools:

- mzml2isa, nmr2isa documentation⁶⁴
- Manuscript in preparation about nmrML being prepared by IPB
- ISA API documentation⁶⁵
- ISA Specifications⁶⁶

Delivered in this reporting period

- D8.3 “nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules”

Future Plans

Work already started towards:

- D8.2 “Modularized ISA model and format: biospecimen centric schema, corresponding xml schemas, reference implementation guidelines and validation rules” at M24.

Work to begin on:

- D8.4 “Signal processing and analysis data exchange format”
- D8.4.1 “Specifications for derived data matrices and terminology for description of analysis and statistical results”
- D8.4.2 “Reference implementation guidelines and validation rules”

WP9 – Tools, workflows, audit and data management

WP leader: Leibniz Institute of Plant Biochemistry (IPB)

The goal of WP9 is to develop and maintain the primary scientific- and technological tools and corresponding interfaces. We establish tools for phenomics, metabolomics and bioinformatics processing pipelines and workflows.

The user is interacting with web interfaces, where we offer Galaxy as a visual workflow engine and Jupyter for interactive explorative analysis in R and Python. The user

⁶⁴ <http://2isa.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶⁵ <http://isatools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶⁶ <http://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

interfaces call into containerized tools, which are running on the container management framework Kubernetes, which in turn is running either locally or in the cloud.

The main achievements during this period are:

- Tool developments
- Workflow developments:
- Automated workflow testing
- Release preparations

A series of weekly workflow demonstrations was held in January/February 2017, with the aim of

- Preparing workflows for the first release “Alanine”
- Providing peer-review and comments for the actual workflows
- Discuss the requirements for documentation/tutorials for workflows

A summary of the progress of work in this period, broken down by tasks:

Task 9.1: Data processing pipelines

We have integrated the W4M pipeline for processing the data from 1) mass spectrometry and 2) NMR instruments.

Task 9.2: Data analysis pipelines

Sacurine workflow:

The workflow performing the statistics in the Sacurine workflow has been adapted to use the MetaboLights download tool, and was demonstrated in January within the project. For the Sacurine⁶⁷ use case, four Galaxy tools from the Workflow4Metabolomics⁶⁸ e-infrastructure (W4M) have been containerized: univariate⁶⁹ (univariate hypothesis testing), multivariate⁷⁰ (OPLS multivariate modeling), biosigner⁷¹ (selection of molecular signatures for diagnostic) and LCMS matching⁷² (LC/MS annotation). Furthermore, a tool (mtbls-dwnld⁷³) was specifically developed for the import data from Metabolights into Galaxy workflows. This module connects to the MetaboLights database and download either a full study (including raw data), or the ISA-Tab files only (thus avoiding transfer of unnecessary files of high volume). The tool was also designed to convert the data from ISA-Tab files into the format required by the

⁶⁷ DOI:[10.1021/acs.jproteome.5b00354](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.5b00354)

⁶⁸ <http://workflow4metabolomics.org/>

⁶⁹ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/univariate>

⁷⁰ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/multivariate>

⁷¹ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/biosigner>

⁷² <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/lcmsmatching>

⁷³ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/mtbls-dwnld>

subsequent modules in the workflow. The modules were containerized in the same way as the other four tools.

The containerization and the development of code tests for the Jenkins Continuous Integration instance, were straightforward. This work thus paves the way for the future containerization of the many Galaxy tools developed by the omics communities.

The Sacurine use case is a sub-workflow from the W4M00001_Sacurine-statistics workflow referenced in W4M. The five modules described previously were successfully chained as a workflow, applied to the MTBLS404 data, and run on the cloud. The demonstration of the running of a real metabolomics workflow on the cloud is a step forward towards a higher reproducibility and computing performance of metabolomics data analysis. This achievement was made possible by the joint work within PhenoMeNal of key European teams, including CEA and W4M (workflow and tools), EBI (MetaboLights repository of raw data; EMBASSY Cloud), and UOXF (definition of data standards).

National Phenome Centre (NPC) workflow

ICL has been working with other partners to containerize local tools and implement pipelines currently used in the UK National Phenome Centre. In this period, a tool for power and sample size calculation⁷⁴ has been containerized, and work to integrate this within PhenoMeNal App Library is ongoing. In addition, the NPC NMR pre-processing and quality control pipeline has been containerized. The latest development includes demonstration of an NMR workflow including NPC preprocessing, followed by analysis by BATMAN for deconvolution and quantification of metabolites. This has been demonstrated on a local installation of the PhenoMeNal infrastructure, as an instance of local processing of sensitive data.

MetFrag workflow: We began with implementing a workflow that imports MS/MS data from MetaboLights and pre-processes these data prior to the actual processing with the tool `metfrag-cli` (which is a command line Galaxy wrapper for MetFrag⁷⁵).

Task 9.3: Data integration and Management

We have started to implement MetaboMatching⁷⁶, a tool for automated metabolite identification in metabolome-wide genome-wide association studies (mGWAS) that use untargeted NMR metabolome data as phenotypes.

⁷⁴ DOI:[10.1021/acs.analchem.6b00188](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.6b00188)

⁷⁵ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/metfrag-cli>

⁷⁶ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/app-library/metabomatching>

Task 9.4: Data Integrity, Audit Trail and Quality Control

The Galaxy workflow engine is recording the tool versions used for the data analysis. The tool wrapper version is recorded in the history ("Galaxy Tool Version" field in GUI's dataset information screen; tool_version tag in exported json) and also in any workflow that is generated using that tool. On the other hand, the tool version is shown in the GUI's information and is stored in one of the DB tables. Exporting a history with results of a workflow into an archive will contain the data that was processed. This archive can be imported into another Galaxy server, and if the relevant tools are installed one can re-run steps. The versioning of the containers in the VRE enables to re-install an identical environment of a stable release.

Task 9.5: Provide continuous development snapshots with life-cycle management for building, testing, and deploying code, tools, and workflows

During the testing workshop at the EBI in November 2016, we met to discuss and formulate standards and conventions for testing containers, as well as for streamlining current and future releases. As an outcome, we created additional guidelines to meet these conventions in order to ensure sustainability and enforce longevity of containers and the whole technical infrastructure. Since then, a number of container building definitions in our continuous integration server have been upgraded to use the agreements in versioning and testing reached.

Photo 1. PhenoMeNal Developers at the testing workshop at EMBL-EBI.

All development projects host their code in the PhenoMeNal github account, with the established git-flow conventions for software branches, merge strategies and release maintenance. Commits to the branches trigger a build and test sequence on the central PhenoMeNal Jenkins CI test platform, which confirms that the code version passes the tests. The container images are then pushed by the CI server to the PhenoMeNal container registry.

Automated workflow testing. With the development of some standard workflows that are to be shared with PhenoMeNal users at large – e.g., the Sacurine and MetFrag workflows – it becomes important to ensure their correctness. To this end, we have implemented automated workflow testing⁷⁷, thus effectively treating workflows as software and applying our continuous integration and testing procedures to their

⁷⁷ <https://github.com/phnmnl/wft4galaxy>

development. The automation, when appropriate configured, monitors development repositories for changes and responds by running the relevant tests cases – which are defined by input data, a set of parameters and the expected results. The test automation can be integrated with our Jenkins continuous integration platform, thus workflow test results can be presented along with other software tests outcomes.

Task 9.6: Migrate existing prototype software from proprietary environments to open, distributable software of high performance and scalability.

Developments were carried out at ICL on the National Phenome Center processing pipeline, which previously contained modules written in the proprietary Matlab environment, cf. task 9.2 above.

The QC pipeline developed in Leiden was ported over to the Python language, and refactored for easier integration into Galaxy pipelines. The components of the pipeline are currently being tested at different partners.

Tool developments

The number of Services Images (VMI) was increased to 39, including Galaxy wrappers for most of them. The PhenoMeNal App Library which is part of the PhenoMeNal Portal contains now 32 VMIs.

Future Plans

Based on the initial set of tools and workflows, which cover the initial steps of the data analysis, expand in several directions:

- Streamline and scale-up existing workflows to very large datasets.
- Implement additional tools and workflows, focussing on downstream analysis,
- Improve the quality of tool and workflow description, including so-called “interactive galaxy tours”. These are very professionally looking guided tours through a galaxy workflow, controlled by a single YAML file that acts as a "Storybook".

All WP's (joint effort)

PhenoMeNal Release

Lead: Leiden University

In preparation for the first public release a release manager was assigned and together with the involved work package leaders a release document was drafted. The release manager is coordinating the efforts within the different work packages related to the

release by having weekly one-on-one progress meetings with the work package leaders. In addition to the progress meetings the group also organises weekly more in-depth technical meetings to address specific issues concerning the infrastructure, tools and workflows and portal integration.

For the first release, it was decided to start with limited functionality and will be considered a beta release. Included in this release (codename: Alanine) will be two example use cases demonstrating the two initial services Galaxy (standardised workflows) and Jupyter (exploratory data analysis). Both services will be accessible via a secure Virtual Research Environment (VRE) which can be deployed from the Virtual Research Environment Gateway (VRE) to a compatible cloud provider (Google, Amazon).

Figure 13. Screenshot of the Pivotal Tracker⁷⁸ to show some of the different tasks that were accomplished as part of the “Release”

Future Plans

- Stable releases every 6 months
- Additional services, workflows and provider compatibility
- Improve the procedure for releasing new versions of the PhenoMeNal services

⁷⁸ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/about/project-management-tool/>

2.3. Project management during this period

WP1-Management

WP leader: EMBL-EBI

This work package is focused on the technical, financial and administrative management of the project including coordination of the activities of the consortium. The main achievements of the reporting are:

- Follow up joint SAB and industry panel meeting.
- Coordination of meetings of working groups.
- Hackathons for dissemination and knowledge management.
- Tracking overall project progress through KPIs for each WP
- Submission of deliverables on time.
- No reported deviations from the project goals and objectives.

A summary of the progress of tasks is reported below:

Task 1.1 Coordination at the consortium level of the ‘technical’ activities of the project.

Project Meetings

The management continued to provide project guidance via online “Monthly Status Update” meetings. The agenda for these meetings was essentially focussed on the progress updates on individual WPs and decision making in terms of general scientific and strategic management of PhenoMeNal. Separate WP and Cross- WP Hangouts were used to discuss in detail the individual WPs, mitigation of risks (if any) identified, performance metrics, future plans and task distribution amongst the partners. The minutes from meetings were extensively documented in the shared Google drive for direction and future reference. The progress of the overall project was extensively monitored via the Pivotal Tracker.

Autonomous advisory board meetings

As part of the consortium's aim to benefit from the feedbacks and suggestions from experts from the scientific community, a joint SAB and industry panel meeting was organised via WebEx on 23rd November 2016 and was attended by 12 advisors from the SAB and industry panel respectively. The main objective of the meeting was to provide independent advice and peer review on PhenoMeNal strategy and progress, strategies for sustainability and ethical constraints. The bi-annual progress report (D1.4.2) was submitted to the board before the meeting to provide an update on the latest developments in the project.

The meeting included short presentations from the individual WP leaders on their recent progress on PhenoMeNal Services, joint research activities and privacy and ethics followed by an open discussion to seek counsel from the advisors on the current work and future directions. For details about the agenda see Annex 3.5

The panel provided its suggestions representing issues recognised as important including advice on the questions presented to the board by the consortium.

PhenoMeNal sustainability in terms of integration and support from European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) including compliance of PhenoMeNal with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) data principles⁷⁹ were the key discussion points during the meeting.

As part of data privacy and ethics in PhenoMeNal, use of cohorts for data analysis, consent forms and data reuse were considered as deeper issues which would need more ground work and expert advice from people working in the ethics domain.

Workshops and hackathons

To establish PhenoMeNal testing at different levels including tool unit testing, container testing, workflow and infrastructure testing, a PhenoMeNal Continuous Testing Hackathon was organised at EMBL-EBI on 14th-15th November 2016. The objective was to enable establishment of PhenoMeNal testing at different levels:

- Tool Unit testing is good software development practice
- Container testing checks our tool packaging
- Workflow testing checks that tools are still interoperable

⁷⁹ <http://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

- Infrastructure testing checks that the PhenoMeNal infrastructure can be fired up and execute workflows of tools in containers.

Task 1.2 The overall legal, contractual, ethical, financial and administrative management of the consortium.

All the tasks related to the legal, contractual, ethical, financial and administrative management of the project are being performed as indicated in the grant agreement.

A grant amendment was submitted in August 2016 for inclusion of CRS4 as new beneficiary. This amendment included increase in the total person months (PMs) and changes to the description of action as suggested by the review panel in the interim review in March 2016.

CRS4 received the budget transfer as the new beneficiary after the acceptance of the Grant amendment. Bank transfers were also initiated for partners who hosted workshops and/or staff-exchange meetings to balance the pre-financing amount received from the commission.

Task 1.3 Coordination of knowledge management, IPS and other innovation-related activities.

Project Website

The project website was used to disseminate information on latest developments of the project, upcoming events, and personal spotlights in the form of blog posts⁸⁰. A PhenoMeNal YouTube Channel⁸¹ was integrated into the project website under the “Dissemination and Outreach”.

⁸⁰ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/>

⁸¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Uw1cPJcOpfo>

PhenoMeNa meets de.NBI
By Namrata • No Comments • de.NBI, elixir, OpenStack, VRE • Technical, Tools

PhenoMeNa at the West-Life/iNEXT Strategy Forum

FAIRifying Metabolomics and Phenomics data in the EOSC
By Namrata • No Comments • Communications, General, What's new, Workshops • Events, Outreach

"Establishing a node for FAIRifying metabolomics and phenomics data in the European Open Science Cloud" - joint workshop, 9th-10th March in Leiden, co-hosted by PhenoMeNa and the GO FAIR initiative led by Barend Mons, the former chairman of the European High-level group on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The end of the workshop will mark...

Figure 14. Blog posts featured on PhenoMeNa website.

YouTube GB Search

PhenoMeNa Gateway
Cloud Research Environment Portal

Home Cloud Research Environment App Library Help

Home

All libraries in the App Library run within the Cloud Research Environment on the cloud. This simplifies running and maintaining applications.

Access to the Virtual Research Environment is through Open Source scientific web environments such as Galaxy Workflow or Jupyter IPython coding web environment.

Test drive our Cloud Research Environment
Galaxy Workflow or Jupyter IPython

Note that this is a public instance accessible by everyone

An easy to use, cloud based scalable software infrastructure for metabolomic research

Want to give it a go?
Create Cloud Research Environment
Find out more

The open-source App Library provides a service catalogue of free Metabolomic data analysis libraries available within the Cloud Research Environment

With user feedback and ratings it is easier to choose the best software for your analysis

Browse App Library

Tutorial on how to find and use Galaxy application via the PhenoMeNa portal

Phenomenal H2020
Channel settings

24 views

Add to Share More

Figure 15. PhenoMeNa YouTube channels with tutorials

PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment Portal

The PhenoMeNal H2020 Wiki⁸² was moved to PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment (CRE) portal and integrated as “Help” pages.⁸³ The “Help” page was designed to reach the user community and provide information on user documentation, developer documentation and tutorials.

PhenoMeNal Gateway
Cloud Research Environment Portal

Home Cloud Research Environment App Library Help

Help

Feedback / Suggestions

Search for Help

User Documentation

- Vocabulary and definitions in PhenoMeNal
- QuickStart Installation for Local PhenoMeNal Workflow
- Uninstallation of Local PhenoMeNal Workflow

Developer Documentation

- Overview of the PhenoMeNal architecture
- Deploying PhenoMeNal on OpenStack
- e-infrastructure requirements for provisioning PhenoMeNal VRE on local systems
- How to make your software tool available through PhenoMeNal
- Continuous Integration of software tools in PhenoMeNal
- Container testing proposals
- The Guideline for Container GitHub Respository README.md Creation

Tutorials

- Using Docker
- Using docker-compose (Work-in-progress)
- Using Kubernetes (Work-in-progress)
- Using Galaxy with Kubernetes to run containerized tools
- Deploy your workflow with Ansible (Work-in-progress)
- Sacrine Statistical Workflow Tutorial (Work-in-progress)

Figure 16. PhenoMeNal “Help” page on the PhenoMeNal

Open Science

As part of its contribution to the Open Science, a “PhenoMeNal-H2020” community was created and curated by uploading of deliverables, presentations and posters on Zenodo⁸⁴. All publications in scientific journals are open access and available on OpenAire.⁸⁵

⁸² <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki>

⁸³ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/home>

⁸⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/phenomenalh2020/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

PhenoMeNal-H2020 project

Recent uploads

Search PhenoMeNal-H2020 project

November 17, 2016 Presentation Open Access View

Analyzing Big Data in Medicine with Virtual Research Environments and Microservices

Sjuth Ola;

Presentation by Ola Sjuth, Deputy director at Department of Information Technology, Uppsala Multidisciplinary Centre for Advanced Computational Science, at Big Data in Medicine, Uppsala, Sweden.

Uploaded on January 13, 2017

September 21, 2016 Poster Open Access View

Workflows for fluxomics in the framework of PhenoMeNal project

de Atauri Pedro; Moreno Pablo; Selivanov Vitaly; Foguet Carles; Marin Silvia; Neumann Steffen; Cascante Marta;

In the framework of the PhenoMeNal project and e-infrastructures (www.phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/), two workflows were prepared using previously developed programs for analysis of intracellular fluxes from isotopologue distributions. Isotopologue distributions will be available on data repositories in

Uploaded on September 21, 2016

Community

PhenoMeNal
Large-Scale Computing for Medical Metabolomics

PhenoMeNal-H2020 project

PhenoMeNal (Phenome and Metabolome aNalysis)

It is a comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure that will support the data processing and analysis pipelines for molecular phenotype data generated by metabolomics applications. PhenoMeNal will provide services enabling computation and analysis to improve the understanding of the causes and mechanisms underlying health, healthy ageing and diseases.

PhenoMeNal is funded by European Commissions H2020 programme, grant agreement number 654241.

Curated by:
PhenoMeNal

Figure 17. PhenoMeNal-H2020 community on Zenodo.

Task 1.5 Maintaining communications with the commission

The coordinator continued in being the prime link between the consortium and the commission regarding the schedule of deliverables and other important communications.

PhenoMeNal Performance Metrics

The project wide performance metrics to track the progress and impact of PhenoMeNal in the reporting period:

Work package	Performance metric	Achieved	Description
2	Number of MoU or SLA from biomedical infrastructures, national or European metabolomics/-phenome centers and/or biobanks	2	Integration with other infrastructures for sustainability
2	Number of agreements with	5	Five publishers recommend data

	publishers		deposition in Metabolights (integrated PhenoMeNal repository): Scientific Data, GigaScience, PloS, F1000Research and Wellcome Trust Open Research journal
3	Active participation to general biomedical/life science conferences	Presentations and posters in 23 conferences	Outreach to broad user community
4	Number of working groups implemented (at least 2)	2	Two publication in preparation
4	Number of European infrastructures/projects represented in working groups (at least 5)	6	Integration with other infrastructures for sustainability
4	Number of documents produced by working groups (at least 2)	2 in preparation	Will be submitted to peer-reviewed journal as a review
5	Number of sites supporting the project	4	Anchoring in local e-infrastructure

	cloud		providers
5	Number of services in the project cloud	32	Enables basic but complete analysis workflows
5	Number of CPUs available	168	Sufficient for users to perform test-runs. Demanding analysis need to be run on user's own account.
6	Access and hit statistics of the VRC portal	Live statistics ⁸⁶ available on dashboard	
6	Number of available and documented standard protocols ⁸⁷	>20	User training and support
6	Number of online tutorials on the VRC web portal	8	User training and support
7	Data disclosure process and procedure established	Data managers and a data controller nominated	Information governance

⁸⁶ <http://portal.phenomenal-h2020.eu/statistics>

⁸⁷ <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki#phenomenal-users>

8	Release of production grade xml schemas (covered by achieving D8.2-4)	1/3	nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and terminologies
8	Publication of functional specifications (covered by achieving D8.2-4)	2/3	ISA specifications released; mzML/nmrML work released in D8.3
8	Adoption and implementation by academic and commercial entities (> 5)	12/min. 5	ISA being adopted in Imperial National Phenome Centre pipeline, in discussion with the Birmingham Metabolomics center
8	Standards software tool releases	7	3x ISA API, 2x nmrml2isa, 2x mzml2isa releases
8	Import from 3rd-party tools and formats capability	6	Can import from MetaboLights, Metabolomics Workbench, SRA XML (European Nucleotide Archive), Biocrates XML, mzML, nmrML

8	Standard Terminology Enhancement	3	NMRML-CV SIRM-CV QC & Control CV
8	Metadata Standards Extension	1	Extension of ISA Data Matrix support for Fluxomics (ongoing work, revision mode)
9	Number of VM's available to users	44	PhenoMeNal services
9	Number of VM downloads	32	PhenoMeNal services
9	Number of high-profile data analyses that can be fully reproduced using the workflows	1	PhenoMeNal services

Table 4. PhenoMeNal performance metrics

Conclusion:

During the first six months of the project, the PhenoMeNal consortium has adhered to its original project objectives. The tasks were completed on time and are under progress according to the project plan defined during the initial stages of the project. The deliverables and milestones were achieved within the assigned framework of time. No minor or major deviations, critical risks technical or administrative, were identified during this period and the consortium plans to continue its activities towards accomplishing its

aim of an integrated, secure and sustainable e-infrastructure.

3. ANNEXES

3.1. Letter of Support

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8jXYd7n9G-NbnRta3EyZjJ3azA/view?usp=sharing>

3.2. MoU

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B8jXYd7n9G-NRIFXejZYWEhNa3M/view?usp=sharing>

3.3. Guidance for Data Governance Managers

In the award of the grant from the EU, Phenomenal was asked to consider carefully any ELSI (Ethical, Legal and Social Implications) for the use of human data. This includes data which is anonymised, is open, restricted, private etc. ELSI should be considered for all cases of data use.

Phenomenal is an infrastructure project to process data. It is not for storing data. During the development phase we will use data to evaluate the performance of Phenomenal and we will need to consider the ELSI implications of this.

The overall project has a Data Controller (Glen) and each site has a Data Manager. The role of the Data Managers is to obtain the relevant information on data used locally or distributed to other partners and to ensure, in collaboration with the Data Governance Manager, that it is ELSI compliant.

In Deliverables (7.1, 7.2, 7.3, 7.4, 7.5) we have considered ELSI requirements in Phenomenal. As your local Data Manager you should read and understand these Deliverables as this will help to securely manage the data that we will use to test Phenomenal infrastructure. You are responsible for the use (and any abuse) of data you provide or use in Phenomenal.

If you intend to use data, you should be aware of the terms of use – for example, you may use open data from Metabolites, which comes under the EBI terms of use, or other data may have restrictions on how it can be used or distributed.

If you provide data e.g. for testing proposes by another group in Phenomenal, you should follow the guidelines in the Deliverables (flow charts, terms of use of Phenomenal, data submission forms) to make the data available under the ELSI constraints and consent given for the use of this data at your institution.

We will hold a registry of the data used in Phenomenal and also the consent that goes with the data. The consent may be a number of documents including ethical approval, patient consent, terms of use etc. Before using or making data available, we should be satisfied that what we are doing is compliant. The following information is needed:

1. Please supply a description of the data
 - a. Who is the main contact for the data (should be a Data Manager)
 - b. What is the data
 - c. Source of the data
 - d. Is it open or restricted

- e. Does it contain patient metadata
 - f. Can an individual be identified from the data
 - g. Where will the data be used (local institution or distribution list)
2. Please supply the consent, NMOU's, DACS's and other documentation that goes with the data and confirm that the data is being used in accordance with these. This will be stored along with the data description.

Data Managers in Phenomenal

PARTNER	DATA MANAGER
EMBL-EBI	Kenneth Haug
ICL	Robert Glen
IPB	Daniel Schober
UB	Pedro de Atauri
UoB	Karen Atkins
CIRMMP	Leonardo Tenori
UL	Michael van Vliet
UOXF	Philippe Rocca-Serra
SIB	Sven Bergmann
UU	Kim Kultima
BBMRI	Petr Holub
CEA	Etienne Thévenot
INRA	Fabien Jourdan
CRS4	Marco Enrico Piras

Software tool to evaluate data use:

Biomedbridges makes available an assessment tool for data provision taking account of ELSI requirements. This may be useful to evaluate your position with respect to data that you wish to provide or use in Phenomenal. <http://hhu2.at.xencon.de:8080/lat/tool>

3.4. Agenda PhenoMeNal Joint Scientific Advisory and Industry Board Meeting

Date: 23rd November

Time: 4:00 - 5:00 PM (UK time)

Pre-meeting documents : [PhenoMeNal bi-annual progress report \(D1.4.2\)](#)

Objective:

To provide independent advice and peer review on PhenoMeNal strategy and progress, strategies for sustainability and ethical constraints

Appointment of the Chair for Advisory Board

Kick off and Update of the project (5 mins)

Chris Steinbeck - (Coordinator PhenoMeNal, EMBL-EBI)

Update on PhenoMeNal Services: operation and maintenance of PhenoMeNal Grid and PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community (5 mins)

Pablo Moreno (EMBL-EBI)

Key Questions:

- Through the use of the technologies implemented, can PhenoMeNal fill the gap between end-users (researchers) and existing RIs like Indigo DataCloud, EGI, HelixNebula, etc?
- How should we engage the nascent EOSC?
- Should we present our achievements generically enough to show that they can be reutilized for other omics/domain fields?

PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway (EMBL-EBI) (5 mins)

Ken Haug (EMBL-EBI)

Key Questions:

- At a later stage willing to be part of beta testing?
 - By default give all users a Elixir SSO account?
-

Update on PhenoMeNal joint research activities: tools, workflows, audit and data management (5 mins)

Steffen Neumann (IPB)

Key Questions:

- Should we aim for PhenoMeNal certification / endorsement of 3rd party tools (converters, data analysis, ...) ? If yes, how official ?
 - How do you see the options in licensing and deployment questions for proprietary software (vendor libraries, Windows, ...) ?
-

Update on Privacy and Ethics in PhenoMeNal (5 mins)

Robert Glen /Tim Ebbels (ICL)

Key Questions:

- Who should we be talking to, to provide ELSI influence and invite to the next Workshop?
 - What ELSI considerations do the SAB see as high priority?
-

Discussion on key topics

- Integration and support from European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for overall sustainability of PhenoMeNal
- Offers to beta-test our PhenoMeNal VRE in local infrastructures